

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM
BB– 2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT #2 – CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

COMPANY – IDEAL MULTIFEED FARM (B) SENDIRIAN BERHAD

MODEL – DIGITAL HRM MODEL

MUHAMMAD SAHRIZ AZIM BIN SAHRUN

17B8113

**LECTURERS: PG DR SITI ROZAIDAH BINTI PG HJ IDRIS & DR WARDAH AZIMAH
BINTI HAJI SUMARDI**

DUE DATE: 11TH NOVEMBER 2020

TABLE OF CONTENT

CONTENT	PAGE NUMBER
Abstract	3
The Problem Statement	3 – 4
The Introduction	4 – 5
Case Analysis	5 – 8
Recommendation & Conclusion	8
List of References	9

Abstract

In this 21st Century, the world has moved into a brand new phase in the modern era of even more advancement than the previous 20th Century. With technologies as the prominent medium in the modern way of life are getting more advanced, traditional methods are getting less and less practiced. Now into 2020, the world has entered Industrial Revolution 4.0 and almost everything has been digitized, primarily affecting the way the business world works. As we look into the business side of things, the managements system associated within in – be it to be expected or not are also prone to transformation, this includes the Human Resource Management system. The traditional and practical way of managing Human Resource (HR) now, is, unfortunately no longer the sole focus in determining a company’s success and performance since the coming of technological advancement. Companies now have to start including and implementing a predicted yet revolutionary Digital Human Resource Management (DHRM) system as part of their management now in order to continue to strive in this technological world. This case study essay will be focusing on the possibility of how Digital Human Resource Management model can be implemented and perhaps assist the traditionally practiced but decades strong local family-based agripreneurial company to be in parallel direction and standing with the other companies in this modern era. It covers most aspects of Digital Human Resource Management Model such as digital employees, digital training and learning, digital communication and potential leadership development.

The Problem Statement

Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad is the featured agripreneurial company for this case study analysis. Based on the company current managing director, Haji Awang Ahmad Morshidi bin Pehin Orang Kaya Di-Gadong Seri Diraja Dato Laila Utama (POKDSDDLU) Haji Awang Abdul Rahman, he identified couple of challenges and problems that they currently faced namely the rising competitions from the same type of companies; affecting their way of raising profits, the various complains regarding the pricing of their high quality products and finally the limited number of supply for a higher number of demand. Although all these problems and challenges faced are not totally new for companies that provide these kinds of services, the possible solutions however, still remain the same, as we need to go back and look through the

management structure of it, particularly its Human Resource area where most of their primary workforces are located. Perhaps with the possible implementation of Digital Human Resource Management Model into the company's HRM, we can see a significant number of possibilities of reducing, if not tackling these challenges that they currently struggling with. With that said, the following sections below will be discussing about tackling the company's in focus challenges with the application of Digital Human Resource Management Model.

The Introduction

Digital Human Resource Management

What is Digital Human Resource Management? It is actually the *digital transformation* of Human Resource (HR) services and processes through the use of social, mobile, analytics and cloud technologies (Rouse, 2018). Simply said, it is the migration of the old, traditional and practical way of managing things into a modern, much lighter, cost efficient way of management system. Apart from that, not only it gives the company a modern touch to their overall management style but also the way the other companies perceive their general evaluations and opinions.

Digital Human Resource Management has been around since social media is a thing back in the 2010's where everything has begun to be digitized and social media became one of the most important medium of communications as well as for doing business. Digital HRM is meant to improve both employee experience and organizational success by transforming the HR function from paper-based, reactive and time consuming to digital-first, mobile and optimized (Rouse, 2018). Its goals include improving employee engagement and retention and measurably augmenting the success of an organization by continually transforming in an agile way (Rouse, 2018).

Ideal Multifeed Farm (Brunei) Sendirian Berhad

According to the book titled '*Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*' written by Musa et al that was published in 2020, the company Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad was founded by

the late Pehin Orang Kaya Di-Gadong Seri Diraja Dato Laila Utama Haji Awang Abdul Rahman, the father of current managing director Haji Awang Ahmad Morshidi, and Mr Toh Soon Hwa. Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad's main service is producing and supplying Halal poultry meat and graded eggs to suppliers like supermarkets and restaurants throughout Brunei Darussalam. It was established on 16th July 1969. During the earlier days decades ago, Ideal Multifeed Farm produced about 5000 graded eggs and slaughtered 200 heads of broiler chickens per day. Nowadays, with their business growing and expanding locally, Ideal Multifeed Farm now produces about 110,000 eggs and slaughtered 7700 heads of broiler chickens per day.

We move on to the business management side now, according to the current managing director of Ideal Multifeed Farm, Haji Awang Ahmad Morshidi, he said that a company's success is contingent upon management skills and a know-how. The managing director also believes that with proper management, that is if you can manage your employee well, their performance will be reflected in their farm's production. This directly triggers the need of a possible application and implementation of Digital HRM Model to the said agriprenurial company.

Case Analysis

As mentioned in the abstract as well as the problem statement sections above, Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad is currently facing a number of common yet serious challenges and problems, particularly in meeting their customers demand, concern on their ways of generating profits with the growing number of rival companies and also overall service satisfaction. As stated, a number of new poultry farm and egg producing companies have multiplied over the years as agricultural industries grown as a result of industrial revolution and globalization in general. For Ideal Multifeed Farm, this problem is definitely not new to them as all businesses are constantly facing this kind of challenges, but what is worrying the agriprenurial company is the fact that not only they are faced with numbers of local rival companies, the international/ outside companies also have begun to shift their eyes into entering the local market and this pose to be one of the biggest concern for the company.

In terms of Digital Human Resource Management Model, before trying to apply and adopt this modern way of human management practice, we first need to know what it consists of that is its elements. According to the 2 authors of *Digital Human Resource Management* article in book titled *GYAN MANAGEMENT* Vol. 11, Issue 2, Sharon & Aggarwal, December 2017, the Digital HRM elements are consist of 1) Digital Employees, 2) Digital Work & 3) Digital Employee Management. The first one is Digital Employees, they are employees that made up of millennials generation and considered as digital natives. They are more inclined to the usage of internet and social media. This means that, they have digital competencies, which is one of the required ingredients in this digital era that could be tapped for better business performance. Second is Digital Work; routine and manual works that are turned digitally will help the organization to grow and cater to known and local areas but also towards remote areas. Third is Digital Employee Management; this involves planning, implementing and using digital technologies to support human resource activities. This will help to reduce certain costs that are involved in managing human resource activities manually, improve the speed of functioning, reduction in errors and so on.

Moving on to discussing the potential of implementing the Digital HRM Model into Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad, the next paragraph will be elaborating on the 3 main challenges the company face and with it comes along the potential solution(s) on how implementing the Digital HRM Model could assist it to perhaps stand on the same level as the other leading companies who have adopted Digital HRM Model much earlier.

Firstly, we are going to look on the first challenges mentioned by the managing director, Haji Awang Ahmad Morshidi. The competition among rival poultry farm and egg producing companies is highlighted. He believes that it is important to ensure that the customers are getting their money's worth by ensuring the chickens and eggs they produced are of high quality according to standard and are consistent throughout (Musa et al, 2020). If we were to adopt the Digital HRM Model to solve this particular problem, it would be beneficial to firstly organize the duty roster of every employees in which they will be having their own shifts. This is to ensure everyone has equal Quality Work Time (QWT) in which if every workers' work time is well managed, their morale is up and productions will increase too.

Secondly, looking on the next challenge faced by Ideal Multifeed Farm is the number of complains that they are receiving from customers due to the pricing of their high quality and premium products. As we can understand from the context above, customers are not feeling satisfied with the pricing of the products despite it being high quality produce, this brings us to theorize that customers need to be constantly updated of the pricing given by the company. In relation to adopting Digital HRM Model, this problem can certainly be reduced, if not solved by transitioning from traditional advertisements and marketing into a digital one. For instance, creating their own social media accounts run by either the marketing department or the HR department. The purpose of transitioning to digital advertising is that to notify its customers on a regular basis regarding their products pricing as we all may already know that most companies and customers are definitely own at least one social media account. Furthermore, this helps to avoid confusion among customers who are planning to make the company as their go-to suppliers by updating them the price constantly on the social media.

Finally, the third and probably the most important challenges to tackle is the limited amount of supply versus the high number of demands. This is where Digital HRM Model plays its part in improving more of Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad. First and foremost is by adopting the model and start including the element of Digital HRM mentioned above especially in turning most of its traditional routine digitally. When they start transitioning mostly to digital, their areas coverage will expand significantly, covering the known as well as the remote areas, information will be gathered much more efficient and simpler without the need to manually sending their workers to scout the area for days. With wide coverage of areas gathered, it is now easier for them to plan their next step into meeting customers demand. Once sufficient information collected from local companies overall, they can start looking for smaller companies with the same production and outsourcing them for more supplies. This way, bit by bit the limited number of supplies versus the higher amount of demands can be reduced as the company is undergoing expansion.

Nevertheless, as advanced and helpful the Digital HRM Model is to solving or reducing the company's problems and challenges, it also comes with some disadvantages as well. The main disadvantage that the company has to go through upon adopting is to either hire more millennials generation that are much more digitally competence (which requires less training on

digital knowledge) or invest on training programs to the already hired/existing employees regarding the digital knowledge which could cost vary depending on how advance the digital knowledge level is. The other problems and cons that Ideal Multifeed Farm could possibly face are the constant update on the digital world and its information such as all the current trends that keep changing monthly according to the global events and so on.

Recommendation & Conclusion

Last but not least, in order to close the case study analysis for Ideal Multifeed Farm (B) Sendirian Berhad with the implementation of Digital HRM Model, the company itself needs to be updated on the current trend of the business world and it is none other than the evolvement of traditional business into online business. While it is true that the company needs to adopt the Digital HRM Model approach in order to solve its current problems and challenges, the optimal solution firstly is to study the needs of the market and assess what steps or potential solutions that could be the most effective according to the nature of the business itself, in this case the production of poultry meats and graded eggs. The very best of solution does not necessarily have to be expensive and changing immediately like transitioning fully from manual methods to digital. It is how the solutions can be beneficial for the health and long running of the company in the years or decades to come.

List of References:

Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.

What is digital HR? - Definition from WhatIs.com. (2020). Retrieved 10 November 2020, from <https://searchhrsoftware.techtarget.com/definition/digital-HR>

Sharon & Aggarwal (2017). *GYAN MANAGEMENT* Vol. 11, Issue 2. *Digital Human Resource Management* article.